

Social Organization of Yin-net Ethnic Group

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Abstract

This research attempts to focus on social organization of Yin-net ethnic group living in villages of Namsan Township, Loilin District, Southern Shan State. They are descendants of Mon-Khamar language family. They are used to wearing traditional dresses and never wear modern dresses. Piercing the ears is a striking feature for males. By means of the ears, males can be identified whether they are single or married. There are mana and taboo for marriage, pregnancy and confinement, and so there are a few cases for inheritance and divorce. The objectives of the research are to preserve the heritage of their ancestors and to maintain the traditional culture as a whole.

Introduction

There is substantial evidence concerning how a national ethnicity descended since prehistoric time, that is, Stone Age, Bronze Age and Iron Age. Although culture is dynamic in lapse of time, their origins remain firmly. According to world history records, there are many language families such as Caucasian, Latin, Ethiopian, European, Indo-European, Mongolian, Hittites, Mediterranean, etc.

Those ethnicities numbering over one hundred who live in Myanmar descended from Mongoloid stock and they came into Myanmar as Mon-Khmer, Tibet-Bamar and Thai-Chinese. The Republic of the Union of Myanmar is the amalgamation of traditions and cultures of these ethnicities. They have their age-old traditions and literature. Their own cultures and art differ so long as habitats favor. But these cultures have linked somehow to reveal social life of Yin-net ethnic group living in Southern Shan State and a field research is done.

Background History of Yin-net Ethnic Group

Among one hundred National ethnic groups living in Myanmar, Yin-net ethnic group descended from Mon-Khmer. There were three waves of migrations called Mon-Khamar, Tibeto-Burman and Tai-Chinese that came into Myanmar and Southeast Asia. But Mon-Khamar were those who first migrated into Myanmar and South East Asia. Mon-Khamar are in fact Austro-Asiatic, subgroup of Austric stock. There are Mon, Palaung, or Ta-ang, Wa, Yin-net, or Yinet, Yin-kya and Danaw ethnic groups in Austro Asiatic language family.

Yin-net is one ethnic group from Mon-Khamar language family. The settlement areas of Mon-Khamar are Lower Myanmar in which Mon live and Southern Shan State where Palaung or Ta-ang, Wa, Yin-net and Yin-kya settle. Since over one hundred years ago, Yin-net and Yin-kya ethnic groups have migrated from hilly regions such as Kyauk-me district, Northern Shan State to certain favorable areas. Yin-kya firstly moved to Southern Shan State and later so did Yin-net.

Now Yin-net ethnic group live in Namho, Namhai, Konelan, Konepok, Naunghe, Naungho, Lwekat, Lwengin, Loisaung, Wankwin, Wanpok, etc, Namsan Township, Loilin District, Southern Shan State. They also live in Kyu-yon Village and neighboring hills two miles away from Pinlon University, Pinlon Township and villages in Kyethe-mansan region.

The Yin-net ethnic group call themselves Yan-lunt or Yin-net that means "people wearing black color clothes". Myanmar call Yin-net as Yin and Shan name Yanlan, meaning

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“black national race”. Yin-net, Yin-kya, Yan Phait and Yan-kyaut are four kinds of Yin brothers. Some call Kayin-net. Yin-net call Myanmar as Mayan and Shan as Syam. Since the time of their ancestors, Yin-net assume they have descended from Kyansittha, a Myanmar King and Nan Mya Oo Sa, a daughter of farmer.

Dress Styles of Yin-net Ethnic Group

For mode of dress of Yin-net ethnic group living in neighboring villages of Namsan Township Southern Shan State, they have been wearing traditional dress since a long time ago. The dress is home spun. The dye is made from barks and black leaves of local plants. Black is their most favorite color and it is used because of absorption of heat, protection from weather, moderation of tinge and weathering. Although wearing black was preferred before, Yin-net youths are wearing other colors at present.

Yin-net males wear long and short sleeve shirts. The dress is decorated with embroidery and beads. Pants are baggy and belt is tied around waist. The length of the pants is three-quarter. Lower and middle parts of the pants are stitched with two or three lines of embroidery. The headpiece is about four yards in length and one foot and six inches in breadth. Piercing the ears is a striking feature for Yin-net males. But left ear is pierced and an earring of certain jewel is worn. By means of the ears, males can be identified whether they are single or married. The national costume of Yin-net female is blouse of V-shaped neck with long or short sleeves. The front part from breast to waist is decorated with woolen tassels drapery and sleeves are trimmed with embroidery. Silver coins are worn around neck. Now some affluent Yin-net maidens embellish their teeth depending on their wealth. Their headpiece is black. The longyi is wrapped and tied with a rope around waist. The upper part is turned upside down like a skirt and over it a cane loop painted with resin is worn. It is found that not only Yin-net elders but also adults and even children are not accustomed to wearing fashionable dress but traditional dress. They believe that wearing their traditional dress brings faithfulness and loyalty to their ethnic group in safeguarding their culture and national race character.

The Life of Bachelor and Maiden

There are three kinds of court occasions – going to a maiden’s house and sitting around the fireplace, courting during religious occasions and courting while doing agricultural activities. In the very first one, a group of Yin-net bachelors go to a Yin-net maiden in a group. They blow flute made of bottle gourd while courting and they court in a group or individually. If a certain bachelor falls in love with a maiden of another village, he seeks for help from the head of bachelors.

The head of bachelors accompanies him to go to the house of the maiden and introduces him and lets them speak near the fireplace. It is their custom, and parents and siblings never interfere and remain silently. The bachelor can tell for a moment or all night so long as he speaks. The maiden does not have the chance to drive him out.

The maiden is to speak all bachelors who woo her; she serves them with betel, tobacco, plain tea and salt. Although she becomes drowsy, she listens to them patiently. She behaves herself without retorting or declining. In having a chat, Yin-net youths use traditional lyrics, verses and riddles in turn. The calibre of a bachelor depends on his courting duration: if he is eloquent, he can tell a girl for a long time and vice versa. If a maiden selects one of the bachelors, the remaining ones go to another house. If she denies that she does not love or like

him, she can politely and tactfully retract. The man who thus suffers pain in love never returns to that house.

In religious and ritual occasion, bachelors and maidens meet, they court at rites and festivals of neighboring villages. They have a chat from the start of the play till morning. It is because Yin-net villages are far from one another. When harvest is over, they have right to court freely. Then while engaging agricultural work together, male youths court female ones when they go along the way to the farm or they have their meal.

Nowadays, Yin-net males bring cassette, torch light, watch, mirror and silver sword. As a token of love, they present those things to the ones they love. They play cassette tapes to enjoy music they like. Torch light is used to signal the girl and so is the mirror. If a Yin-net maiden loves him, she presents a Yin-net bag for him as a token of affection.

Although Yin-net male and female love each other very much, they are married with the consent of parents. Elopement is rare enough, they never make love affairs, although they are free enough to court in the girl's house, see at performance or cultivation work. So, a Yin-net male esteems and adores the girl he wants to marry.

Marriage

Although a Yin-net male falls in love with a Yin-net female, they get married only when their parents give consent. A Yin-net male, together with parents, some elderly people and friends, goes to the house of his lover to get consent for the betrothal of her parents. The Yin-net male excitedly awaits the news of betrothal on the house or under the house. When the male's party tell the female's side about the betrothal. In doing so, the party of the male gives brass betel box and a towel to marry a maiden.

When the other party give approval, Yin-net maiden brings her belongings, goes along with her lover and she has spent three nights at her lover's house. After that, they pay respects to parents together with three or four elders from their quarter. Parents invite three or four elders. In this aspect, popcorn, pickled fish, molasses bars, betel, lime, tobacco leaves, coconut, bananas, ten bottles of liquor, pan and five tickles of pickled tea leaves are necessary to be included. Parents and elders pray for well-being in their following days. Then one of the elders announces the two youths as eligible husband and wife and then wish for peaceful and eternal union till last breath. In marriage, money is not a very essential thing. Some well-to-do males hold wedding ceremony but some hold by serving with liquor and guests are given packets of pickled tea with molasses bar. After the ceremony they live either patrilocally or matrilocally on account of few members of the family. If the bride accompanies with her spouse, a banquet is provided at the bride's house. If the groom comes to live at his mate's house, parents of the groom are paid respects with traditional offertory. Then liquor is served. If Yin-net folk elopes with the one whom parents do not agree with, compensation is given to parents of the girl. Compensation is known as 'let-sae-pae' in Yin-net term. It is about 30000 or 40000 kyats. In this case, liquor is essential in addition to money. Then, as Yin-net ethnic group live in cold regions, not only men but women drink a small amount of liquor. So, liquor is a very important item for giving treatment on an auspicious occasion as well as on inauspicious one.

In order to maintain their lineage, Yin-net practice endogamy. They do not marry other lineage. They can marry cousins of their ethnic group. For example, children of mother-sisters and father-brothers are not allowed to marry. If they breach, they are regarded as animals. This is the key prohibition in marriage of Yin-net; Cross-cousin – children of father and his sister and those of mother and her brother are able to marry. But parallel cousins – children of mother-sisters or father-brothers are to treat one another as one's own brother or sister. Other

Yin-net lineages are entitled to get married. Certain auspicious days are selected for wedding but during lent, marriage is prohibited as Myanmar do. Through wedding ceremony of Yin-net ethnicity, it is seen that they maintain loyalty and esteem of their lineage and their tradition.

Pregnancy

There are mana (do's) and taboo (don'ts) for pregnant women since pregnancy. Not to face weight loss of the baby and breach delivery Yin-net pregnant women abstain from eating sticky rice, leftovers and over eating sweet-meat. They also restrain from eating more bananas that make the baby grow overly. They then take care of themselves not to be troublesome. They avoid sewing pillows, blocking holes, sitting at the centre of door, case sitting toward kitchen, napping in day time, going outside at dusk, etc. If they go out for some reasons, at such time, safety pin is placed in hair so as to exorcise evil spirits and devils.

A husband of a Yin-net woman who is pregnant abstains from performing such activities as shouldering bier and giving a hand in inauspicious tasks. Such tasks make their wives deliver their babies with difficulty. But expectant mothers, till due date, go to farm with their spouses and manage to work there. They go to the farm daily without resting comfortably at home. They do some light works such as pounding paddy or farm work all day. According to belief, the way to the farm is situated in the mountainous area so it demands a lot of physical movements and these tiring movements make them deliver their babies without pain. Only when due date is near, they remain at home. They do not take any western medicine. These things are do's and don'ts of Yin-net expectant mothers have.

Child Birth

Yin-net women bear their babies with the aid of midwife at home. Now nurse in village dispensary helps expectant mother confine. If there is difficulty in confinement, broom is soaked with water, the abdomen is rubbed with the water down her feet and the midwife mutters herself, 'thrust, thrust' and it is believed that such act makes her easy to deliver. In delivery, some experienced ladies and neighbors helped her confinement.

After delivery, the umbilical cord is cut with bamboo strip and the navel is rubbed with gooseberry paste. The father himself buries the umbilical cord under the stair case of a house. If the cord is not buried, when the baby grows old, it is believed, he leaves from his nativity and settles down in the other region. After birth she remains in a room furnished with a fireplace to keep her warm. Then it makes her sweat and blood purified and she then rejuvenates.

In this case, Yin-net women use a certain kind of wood called mite-lwek so that they will have good circulation of blood and get new energy. If they fail, they feel chilly and cold later in their lives. Their knuckle bones ache and nerves of hands and legs become strained. Some Yin-net ethnic group keep a separate delivery room. But some keep warm near fireplace in the centre of the house. It is surrounded by wood. In the centre of fireplace, the earth is placed and three pieces of brick are laid on the embankment and firewood is burnt.

After delivery, they take their traditional medicine. Long ago, mothers gave midwife some presents such as clothes, dried tea leaves, bunch of bananas, and cash etc. They wash hands of midwife with soapberry juice. Bad blood and other dirt smeared in delivery need to be cleansed with soapberry juice. Seven days after confinement, the midwife is treated with meals. Mother abstains from eating harmful foods and keep diets such as pepper, chilli, etc., in having meals. She sips soup of ginger and salt, that of turmeric and salt, and rice and baked

salt. Three months after confinement she can eat various kinds of fruits and vegetables, meat and fish. She avoids eating internal organs till months after delivery.

Childhood of Yin-net

Yin-net ethnic group have no naming ceremony. A certain experienced man names the child suitably. At the age of two, the child is called by his name. At that time mother takes her child to the monastery to tread on its ground. It is believed that only when the child does, he will have good health. Yin-net boys are given the name of 'ta-ai' and girls 'E-aung' and so on.

The infant is nestled in her when she goes to the farm. Some elder children are looked after by grandparents. When children start to hobble, they are taught the name of things around them. As Yin-net ethnicities live in mountainous regions, they are accustomed to playing on the mountains with respect to their customs.

When they are old enough, parents train them to help in farm work. They learn how to burn the stumps and slash, grow and harvest the crops, offer traditional spirits such as spirits of farmland, river, etc., trap birds, hunt animals, search medicinal herbs, and treat strip tree barks in search of wood to build houses and its roof. Yin-net youths are thus acculturated in all art. They are taught so that their skills will be perfect and they can participate not only in parental business but in communal activities.

Yin-net girls under the guidance of their mothers are trained to look after younger siblings, make fire to cook, fetch water, and cook meals. They then transplant seedlings, pound rice, and spin and weave traditional costumes etc; thus they are skilful at household chores and agricultural work. They participate in auspicious and inauspicious occasions of the society. Girls are specially trained not to choose inappropriate partner. At night, grandparents or parents tell about traditional beliefs and their rites and rituals.

Inheritance

Elder son or daughter is entitled to take the role of parents. There is no discrimination between males and females. They are given equal rights. Only when a family has no children, nephews and their great-uncles can inherit them. Inheritance is distributed according to wealth. Inheritance is done through parental wish. Sons and daughters get their share at marriage and they are to inherit no more. The rest members of the family work through thick and thin and the bread-winner manages all activities. Those who look after parents have right to claim most or all lion's shares. If any member feels displeased, the village elders can divide shares to all members. As Yin-net ethnic group live peacefully and co-operatively and obey the elders, any cases of inheritance are rarely found.

Divorce

Divorce is simple enough for Yin-net ethnic group. Either husband or wife can claim to divorce on account of low income, discord, infertility etc. No two parties of parents, village elders or friends need to negotiate. When husband or wife returns to his or her parent's home, having no will to love and live together, it is meant for divorce. The rest partner never takes him or her to come back home. But something is committed by the dissented partner, he or she is sued and properties are equally distributed. But the one who leaves the house for divorce has no right to share. The one who is left behind in the house has the right to possess the belonging. When the husband remarries, the ex-wife never asks for fine or compensation. But

father can provide allowance if he has his own wish and mother nurtures her children. Yin-net divorcees are able to marry again. Although they divorce over some matter, they can decide unanimously without being put blame on each other. Most Yin-net national practice monogamy whereas polygamy is found a little.

Conclusion

Most of the people of Yin-net ethnic group live in Namsan Township, Loilin District, Southern Shan State. Anthropologists mainly emphasize activity theory based on history with a focus on feature development. Survey and inquiry are made on daily life situations of Yin-net ethnic group by direct contact system. Some of the facts are collected by subsequent inquiries and investigations of their social pattern and living standard.

Yin-net always wear their traditional costumes so as to remain loyal to their lineage. In adult life, bachelors and spinsters are free enough to meet, they never cheat to make love and esteem virginity. Then through parental approval, they get married so they emphasize parental wish and owe them obedience. Liquor plays a vital role in their tradition, however, they do not lead a wild life and they take liquor so as to gain good health. The expectant mothers have do's and don'ts and children are trained to maintain their traditions through enculturation. In heritage and divorce, as there are a few disagreeable cases, it is known that they live harmoniously. Thus, not only youths but also elders know their tradition and try to maintain their lineage to last longer.

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